

Understanding the degradation of bio-based polymers across contrasting marine environments using complementary analytical techniques

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HIGHLIGHTS

- FTIR-derived indices explained specific abiotic and biotic degradation pathways.
- ΔHm indicated rapid degradation of amorphous regions of PBS in marine sediments.
- T_{peak} and E_a showed a high loss of thermal stability in cellulose-derived polymers.
- Light altered the chemical structure of polymers without affecting mass loss.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Plastic degradation
Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy
Differential scanning calorimetry
Thermogravimetric analysis
Marine environment

ABSTRACT

Biodegradable and compostable polymers have emerged as an alternative to conventional plastics to mitigate environmental problems related to plastic perdurability. However, these materials are certified as biodegradable/compostable following technical standards that consider a limited range of environmental conditions. Therefore, some materials may not degrade as rapidly as expected under certain natural conditions. Understanding degradation patterns of polymers across diverse environments is essential to ensure their sustainable use. We examined the degradation of bio-based materials certified as biodegradable/compostable under various marine conditions, including the seabed and both the euphotic and aphotic zones of the water column, for one year through a comprehensive analytical approach combining weight loss measurements, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy, differential scanning calorimetry and thermogravimetric analysis. Despite the marked different degradation rate between materials, both lost five times more weight in sediment than in the water column, highlighting the influence of environmental compartment on degradation. Although light did not

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2025.146435>

Received 31 January 2025; Received in revised form 1 August 2025; Accepted 14 August 2025

Available online 26 August 2025

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contribute to weight loss, it promoted molecular degradation by modifying chemical structures and thermal properties. Degradation was influenced by material-specific characteristics, with polymers of higher hydrophilicity and lower crystallinity being more prone to degradation. This was evidenced by changes in analytically derived parameters, including shifts in FTIR indices and reductions in maximum degradation temperature, activation energy and crystallinity, highlighting the complementary insights provided by the applied techniques. These findings provide an integrated understanding of degradation processes, supporting the design of more sustainable materials, and contributing to the development of new technical standards that better reflect natural conditions.

1. Introduction

Global plastic production is increasing exponentially every year, reaching 400 million tons by 2022 (Statista, 2024). The 60 % of the plastic produced is discarded and accumulates in landfills and in the environment (Geyer et al., 2017). Oceans are becoming a sink for plastic waste, currently accumulating between 75 and 199 million tonnes of plastics (United Nations Environment Programme, 2021). One of the key characteristics linked to plastic pollution is the perdurability of plastic wastes. Thus, alternative materials such as biodegradable and compostable plastics are being developed, which still represent only the 0.5 % of the total annual plastic production (European Bioplastics, 2023). This type of polymers can be degraded by microbial activity in natural and compost environments, respectively (European Commission, 2022). These characteristics enable to reduce the persistence of the polymers in the environment when they are not properly managed (Nazareth et al., 2019). In addition, as biodegradable and compostable plastics are mainly bio-based, which means that they are fully or partially made by biological resources, their use reduces the utilization of non-renewable fossil sources (Lambert and Wagner, 2017).

Polymer degradation changes the chemical structure, physical properties, or appearance of a polymer, caused by the cleavage of the macromolecules forming the polymer chain (Laycock et al., 2017), and can be triggered by different mechanisms (e.g. photolysis, oxidation, thermal activation, hydrolysis or biological activity) (He et al., 2021). For biodegradable plastics, the degradation process takes place through the action of enzymes associated with microorganisms present in natural conditions, such as bacteria and fungi (Nazareth et al., 2022). Firstly, the polymer is fragmented into fractions of lower molecular mass by exposure to abiotic (i.e., oxidation, photodegradation, hydrolysis), and biotic reactions (i.e., degradation by microorganisms) (Napper and Thompson, 2019). The pace of these abiotic and biotic processes depends on different factors such as the type of functional group, molecular weight, and surface to volume ratio of the polymer (Min et al., 2020). Then, the microorganisms secrete extracellular enzymes that catalyse the depolymerization of the polymer chain into oligomers and monomers (Haider et al., 2019). These small molecules are bio-assimilated and mineralized by microorganisms, forming carbon dioxide, methane, water and biomass (De Falco et al., 2021). Compostable plastics follow a similar degradation process as the one for biodegradable plastics, with the difference that they are degraded in an environment where temperature, aeration and humidity are controlled (Briassoulis et al., 2010; Ruggiero et al., 2020) enhancing their degradability.

The term biodegradability has been widely misused, thus material certification of its biodegradability or compostability has emerged as a tool for validating this characteristic (Nazareth et al., 2022). The biodegradability/compostability of a material is certified when it meets technical standards developed by standardization bodies such as the International Standards Organization (ISO), American Society of Methods and Materials (ASTM), European Standardization Committee (EN), and Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) (Viera et al., 2021). However, technical standards certify the biodegradability of materials in certain conditions without considering the large variety of them in natural environments. As a result, some materials that are certified as biodegradable or compostable, may not

degrade as fast as expected under certain natural conditions. For example, in the case of the marine environment, the certification TUV OK biodegradable MARINE only takes into consideration the photic zone of the water column, not considering other environmental compartments with contrasting environmental conditions (e.g. temperature, salinity, light exposure, and microbial activity) that can significantly influence degradation rates and mechanisms, such as the seabed and the aphotic layer of the water column.

Marine sediments, which harbour larger numbers of microorganisms than the water column, are considered environments that favour degradation (Thellen et al., 2008). In fact, some bio-based materials degrade 10 times more rapidly in the seabed than in the water column (Beltrán-Sanahuja et al., 2020). At the surface of the water column, light can enhance polymer degradation through photodegradation (Delacuvellerie et al., 2021), this effect being attenuated as depth increases. In addition, as the euphotic zone is a well-aerated habitat with high levels of solar radiation the growth of bio-fouling in plastic films is common, which may facilitate the degradation of bio-based plastics by microbial activity (Briassoulis et al., 2019). In contrast, in the aphotic zone the degradation could be diminished due to the lack of light availability. However, little research effort has been made in this compartment. Since oceans receive large amounts of improperly managed plastic waste each year (Jambeck et al., 2015), evaluating degradation under different marine compartments becomes not only relevant from a scientific perspective but also from a regulatory and practical standpoint. This assessment allows for a comprehensive understanding of the environmental impact of biodegradable polymers and supports the development of standardized testing protocols that better reflect real-world scenarios, thereby promoting the development of more sustainable materials that can break down naturally. Polymer degradation can be studied focusing on changes in physical properties (e.g. weight loss over time); in the molecular structure, using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR; e.g. indices to determine the formation of new or disappearance of functional groups in the polymer chain) (Barragán et al., 2016; Skvorčinskienė et al., 2023; Sudhakar et al., 2008) and changes in the thermal properties, using Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC; e.g. melting temperature [T_m], melting enthalpy [ΔH_m], degree of crystallinity) (De Falco et al., 2021; Delacuvellerie et al., 2021), and Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA; maximum degradation temperature [T_{peak}] and activation energy [E_a]) (Ruggiero et al., 2020), among others. However, each of these techniques is designed to characterize specific properties of a material. For example, FTIR can identify chemical changes in the surface of the polymer, but may not provide complete information on the overall degradation process. DSC and TGA can offer insights into thermal stability and crystallinity changes, yet they do not reveal the molecular-scale chemical transformations.

Thus, simultaneously employing all three techniques can provide a more comprehensive understanding of polymer degradation (as described in De Falco et al., 2021), encompassing both molecular and physical changes. Despite the potential advantages of this integrated approach, its application has been relatively scarce in existing research (De Falco et al., 2021). This study introduces a pioneering methodology by combining specific parameters derived from FTIR, DSC, TGA and weight loss measurements to analyze the biotic and abiotic degradation

pathways of two commercial bio-based materials, one certified as biodegradable in the marine environment and the other as compostable, under different marine conditions. To achieve this goal, the degradation of the materials was monitored in the laboratory for one year through a mesocosm experiment in which different marine environmental compartments, including the seabed and the water column (euphotic and aphotic conditions), were simulated. By using this multi-technique approach, this study provides a holistic analysis of the degradation of biodegradable and compostable plastics, advancing our understanding of the complex steps involved in this process.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reference materials

Two commercial bio-based materials with different degradation certifications were selected to compare their degradation behavior under various marine conditions. According to the manufacturer's technical data (Futamura Group; product code: NatureFlex™ NVS), the first material (hereafter referred to as Material A) consists of a transparent cellulose layer coated with a heat-sealable coating. It is semi-permeable to moisture (at 38 °C and 90 % r.h.: 600 gr/m² after 24 h; ASTM E96) and presents an oxygen barrier value measured at 23 °C and 0 % r.h. of 1 cc/m² after 24 h atm (ASTM F1927), a maximum degradation temperature (T_{peak}) of 338 °C and an activation energy (E_a) of 211 kJ/mol. This material meets ASTM D6691-09 test for biodegradability in marine environments and is certified as compostable in both industrial (EN13432, EN14995, ASTM D6400 and ISO 17088) and home (OK Compost Home) composting environments.

The transparent cellulose layer was characterized as cellulose acetate, as the FTIR spectrum showed the presence of acetate groups in cellulose (e.g. the acetyl CH₃ absorbance (1373 cm⁻¹), the acetyl C-O absorbance (1240 cm⁻¹), and the acetyl C=O absorbance (1716 cm⁻¹)) (Fei et al., 2017) (Fig. S1) and presented a coincidence factor (R) of 0.77 with cellulose acetate from the KnowItAll database. Being Material A characterised as possible cellulose acetate, its degree of substitution (DS) was calculated following the methodology (Ribeiro et al., 2022). An initial degree of substitution of 0.6 was obtained, which is a low value compared to usual commercial cellulose acetate (DS = 2.5) (Puls et al., 2011).

As for the second material (hereafter referred to as Material B), the manufacturer's technical data (BIOPAP; product code: PBBIO-PLUS16034501) indicates that it is a bilayer material made of a cellophane-based film and a biopolymer of vegetable origin. This material presents a value of permeability to water vapour measured at 38 °C and 90 % r.h. of 15gr/m² after 24 h and a high oxygen barrier (oxygen permeability at 23 °C and 0 % r.h.: 1 cc/m² after 24 h atm). It is certified as compostable according to EN 13432:2000-12.

The cellophane layer presents an amorphous structure with a T_{peak} of 307 °C and an E_a of 202 kJ/mol. FTIR analysis of this layer showed the typical fingerprint area of the cellulose backbone in the range 800–1220 cm⁻¹, being the peak at 898 cm⁻¹ characteristic of β -glycosidic linkage between glucose units, and the peak at 1061 cm⁻¹ attributed to the C-O group of secondary alcohols and ethers functions that exist in the cellulose chain backbone (Aqil et al., 2015). The peaks at 2906 cm⁻¹ and 1373 cm⁻¹ are assigned to stretching and deformation vibrations of C-H group in glucose unit. The peak at 1730 cm⁻¹ is assigned to ketones, aldehydes, and carboxylic groups, and the band in the 3100–3600 cm⁻¹ region is attributed to the -OH stretching vibration of the hydroxyl groups on the cellulose backbone (Leppänen et al., 2020) (Fig. S2).

The biopolymer of vegetable origin of Material B presents a melting temperature of 112 °C, a T_{peak} of 391 °C and an E_a of 229 kJ/mol. These thermal properties, together with the FTIR spectrum, confirmed that the biopolymer could be poly(butylene succinate) (PBS) (R = 0.78, KnowItAll library). In the FTIR spectrum the band at 1710–1713 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the C=O stretching vibrations of ester groups in poly

(butylene succinate), while the peaks in the range 1224–1292 cm⁻¹ result from the stretching of the -C-O-C- group in the ester linkages (Phua et al., 2013). The peaks at 1330 and 2945 cm⁻¹ are assigned to the symmetric and asymmetric deformational vibrations of CH₂ groups, respectively (Georgousopoulou et al., 2016) (Fig. S3).

Their common use in commercial products makes them relevant for assessing their environmental impact and aligning the study with practical, real-world scenarios.

2.2. Experimental set up

The degradation of materials was tested under three different marine conditions, that were simulated in the laboratory under controlled conditions for one year. The different marine conditions were simulated inside cores made of poly (methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) with internal diameter of 5.4 cm and a height of 18 or 32 cm depending on whether the water column or the seabed were simulated, respectively. Regarding the water column, both the euphotic zone, which refers to the stratum where there is a high availability of sunlight; and the aphotic zone, which refers to the stratum of the water column where the incidence of light is zero, were simulated, using transparent or opaque cores, respectively. The cores were filled with filtered sea water (filter pore size: 0.5 mm) with a salinity of 37.6 psu. Regarding the euphotic zone, a UV lamp (MicMol, AQUA Air 300, China) with a power of 24 W and including all the spectra of natural light, was utilized to simulate the natural sunlight received in the first 10 m of water column (day/night cycle of 12/12 h). Regarding the seabed compartment, the cores were filled with sediment to a depth of 20 cm and were left to stratify for a week before the beginning of the experiment. The remaining 12 cm were filled with filtered seawater. The sediment was obtained from a beach in the western Mediterranean Sea (38°11'018.81" N 0° 35'034.55" W). The specific location of sampling is not expected to influence the results as the degradation pathways analyzed combining the three analytical techniques is specific to each material and allows differentiation between specific processes involved on each environmental compartment (sediment vs. euphotic and aphotic zones of the water column). The sediment was sieved *in situ* through a 0.5 mm screen to remove large organisms/biological fragments (e.g. polychaetes, bivalves, seagrass, shells) and other non-biological components such as gravel and litter. Particle size scales of the sediment range from very fine clay to medium sand (Blott and Pye, 2012). All cores were closed at the bottom with rubber stoppers and secured with high-strength duct tape. The seawater of each core was oxygenated by air pumps and changed once a week to avoid anoxic conditions. The seawater was maintained at 16 °C through two water chillers (HAILEA, model HC-130A and HS-28A) that recirculated the water in the tanks.

Rectangular plastic pieces (3.5 × 1.5 cm) of each material were weighed and introduced into small fiberglass bags with a mesh size of 1 mm, to prevent the loss of material. The bags were closed with cotton thread of different colors to differentiate the type of material and replicate. The cores contained either Material A or Material B. Eight bags were introduced into each core, to test the degradation of each material at 8 sampling times by taking one bag each month during the first 6 months and then after 9 and 12 months. A total of 18 cores were required for the experiment set up (3 environmental compartments x 2 materials x 3 replicates). In the cores simulating the water column, the samples were submerged in the water using marble sphere tied to the bags with cotton thread to keep the bags submerged. In the cores simulating the seabed, the samples were buried in the first 4 cm of the sediment.

2.3. Pretreatment

At the specific months, the fiberglass bags of each material were taken out from the cores and immediately transferred into zip block bags. Then, in the laboratory, each sample was cleaned three times with

distilled water using a sieve of 0.053 mm mesh size to eliminate sediment particles and any biofilm formed in the surface of the polymer, and avoid the loss of fragmented material. The samples were dried at 40 °C for 24 h. Then, analyses of the samples were carried out to monitor weight loss and possible changes in the chemical structure and thermal properties of the polymer, by using FTIR, DSC and TGA.

2.4. Weight loss analysis

The weight loss of each material was calculated following the equation:

$$\% \text{ weight loss: } [(m_0 - m_t) / m_0] \times 100$$

Where m_0 is the initial weight of each sample and m_t is the final weight at the corresponding testing day. All samples were weighted using a precision balance (± 0.0001 g).

2.5. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

The infrared spectra were recorded in total reflectance mode (ATR) using a Bruker Analytik IFS 66FTIR spectrometer (Ettlingen, Germany) equipped with a DTGS KBr detector and a Golden Gate Single Reflection Diamond ATR accessory (incident angle of 45°). The spectra were recorded in the wavenumber range 4000 to 600 cm^{-1} with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and corrected against the background spectrum of air. All spectra were averaged over 64 scans. One spectrum was obtained for each sample of Material A, while 2 spectra (one of each side) were recorded for Material B as it is a multilayer material composed by different materials in each side. The KnowItAll software was used to characterize the polymeric components of the materials, and the coincidence factor (R) was used to analyze the degree of similarity between the spectral library and the materials selected in this work. The FTIR spectra of the studied materials were associated to a specific polymer type of the database when $R > 0.7$. The variation in the intensity of the different peaks and bands was used to evaluate the degradation of the polymers. To do so, different indices were calculated, including the C=O, C-O, C-H and O-H indices depending on the bonds present in each material (specified in section 2.1). To avoid interferences from potential residual biofilm or other surface contaminants, the absorption bands corresponding to each chemical bond were established based on the control plastic (time 0). The indices were defined as:

$$I_x = AX_t / AX_0$$

Where I_x refers to each specific index, AX_t refers to the area of the absorption band of a given bend at a specific time, and AX_0 refers to the area of the absorption band of the same bend at time 0.

Absorption bands used to calculate the indices of each material are shown in Table S1.

2.6. Thermal analysis

To evaluate the thermal properties of the materials, TGA and DSC analysis were performed. Since both DSC and TGA detect bulk thermal properties, the data obtained from these techniques are representative of the intrinsic characteristics of the polymer matrix and are not influenced by potential surface residues or biofilm.

2.6.1. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

For each material, the thermal transitions were obtained by using a DSC Q100 equipment (TA Instruments, USA). Samples (0.5–3 mg) were introduced in aluminium pans (40 μL) and they were heated from 25 °C

to 300 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min under a nitrogen atmosphere. Calorimetric curves were analyzed by using the *Universal Analysis TM* software (TA Instruments, New Castle, USA) to obtain the melting temperature (T_m , °C) and melting enthalpy (ΔH_m , J/g). ΔH_m was obtained from the areas of melting peaks.

2.6.2. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

TGA was performed using a Mettler-Toledo TG-DSC2 (USA) equipment by introducing 0.5–10 mg of the sample into 70 μL alumina pans. The analyses were conducted heating the samples from 30 to 700 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min under inert atmosphere (nitrogen flux = 50 mL/min). The main information obtained from the first derivative of the TGA curves were the characteristic temperatures of the peaks associated to the thermal reactions of the components of each material. These parameters are indicated as T_0 , T_{inf} and T_{peak} and correspond, respectively, to the initial, to the final and to the maximum temperature of every peak. In addition, and following the methodology of Mano et al., (2003), the activation energy (E_a) of the thermal reactions undergone by the different components of both materials was obtained. To calculate the E_a , the Friedman equation was applied:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = A \cdot e^{-E_a/RT} \cdot f(\alpha) \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

where E_a is the activation energy [kJ/mol] of the thermal degradation reaction of the components constituting Material A and Material B, A is the Arrhenius constant, α is equal to $(w_0 - w_t) / (w_0 - w_{inf})$ where w_0 is the weight of the sample before the analysis (when $t = T_0$), w_t is the weight at time t , and w_{inf} is the weight of the sample at the end of the conversion (when $t = T_{inf}$). In addition, n is the order of the reaction, R is equal to 8.314 J/mol·K and T is the temperature (K). $f(\alpha)$ represents the differential conversion function, with its most common form for solid-state reactions being $f(\alpha) = (1 - \alpha)^n$ (Mano et al., 2003). By substituting $f(\alpha)$, equation (1) becomes:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = A \cdot e^{-E_a/RT} \cdot (1 - \alpha)^n \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

By considering $n = 1$ (first order reaction), the integration of Equation (2) becomes:

$$-\ln(1 - \alpha) = A \cdot e^{-E_a/RT} \cdot t + \text{const or} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

$$\ln(-\ln(1 - \alpha)) = \ln(A \cdot e^{-E_a/RT} \cdot t + \text{const})$$

As A and t experimental constants, equation (3) can be simplified to:

$$\ln(-\ln(1 - \alpha)) = -\frac{E_a}{RT} + \text{const} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

If we plot $\ln(-\ln(1 - \alpha))$ vs $1000/T$ through a linear fitting it is possible to obtain $-\frac{E_a}{R}$ that corresponds to the slope of the curve.

2.7. Statistical analysis

The trends of weight loss and the parameters derived from FTIR, DSC and TGA analysis were modelled through time. The model was chosen by adjusting the data to the best-fitting regression model using the Akaike Information Criteria (AIC). The lower the AIC index, the better the model, as it has the best trade-off between goodness of fit and complexity (Table S2). Then, the trends among the different marine compartments were compared using the analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). Statistical analyses were conducted with the R software (v.4.2.3) using the packages “AICcmodavg”, “plyr” and “stringr”. Data are reported as mean \pm standard error (SE). Statistical tests were conducted considering a significant level of $\alpha = 0.05$.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Monitoring the degradation of bio-based materials

3.1.1. Weight loss analysis

After one year of exposure, the weight loss of Material A was significantly higher in marine sediment samples (90.6 ± 5.4 %) than in samples exposed to the aphotic (22.0 ± 4.8 %) and euphotic (9.3 ± 2.5 %) zones of the water column (Fig. 1, Table S3). Material B also exhibited a greater weight loss under sediment (22.9 ± 3.3 %) than under the aphotic (3.8 ± 1.0 %) and euphotic (0.5 ± 0.5 %) zones after one year (Fig. 1, Table S4). In agreement with previous studies (Beltrán-Sanahuja et al., 2020), the results demonstrate that the weight loss of the studied bio-based materials is mainly influenced by the environmental compartment, being the degradation rates ca 4.5 times higher in the sediment than in the water column. Marine sediments harbour 1000 times more microorganisms than the water column (Delacuvellerie et al., 2021; , 1993 Sander and Kalff). This high microbial abundance renders marine sediments crucial environments for the degradation and mineralization of organic matter (Middelburg et al., 1993), including biodegradable polymers and other degradable components.

Regarding degradation in the water column, both materials exhibited a decline in the weight loss trend by the end of the experiment in the euphotic zone, whereas this pattern was less pronounced in the aphotic zone, particularly for Material A, which even showed a slight increase. The reduced degradation observed in the euphotic zone may be attributed to variations in biofilm composition influenced by light availability (Smith et al., 2021), which could modulate the plastic degradation potential of the associated microbial communities. In the euphotic zone, biotic degradation may be reduced due to the availability of alternative carbon sources produced by phototrophs that are more easily metabolized (de Vogel et al., 2024). The accumulation of denser and more structurally complex biofilms over time (Odobel et al., 2021; Marín et al., 2025) could also affect degradation rates, as light-driven primary production favors higher biofilm biomass (Kumar Sen and Raut, 2015; de Vogel et al., 2024). These biofilms could hinder complete removal of attached material (particularly under euphotic conditions) despite standardized cleaning, a known limitation in long-term *in situ* studies. Although the method used to remove biofilm is widely used and accepted, in such cases it may lead to a slight underestimation of weight loss. While this fact does not invalidate the technique, attention should focus on general trends over subtle changes.

The degradation of cellulose acetate (Material A) depends on its degree of substitution (Leppänen et al., 2020). In this sense, the degradation rates are increased when acetylation levels are low (Yadav and

Hakkarainen, 2022) because there are less substituents that can prevent enzymes from attacking the cellulose backbone and degrade it (Fei et al., 2017). As the cellulose acetate tested in this study presents a low degree of substitution (≈ 0.6), ester hydrolysis of acetyl groups (deacetylation) and biological hydrolysis of the cellulose backbone can occur easily (Erdal and Hakkarainen, 2022). Accordingly, the weight loss of inoculated cellulose acetate was 86 % when the cellulose acetate presented a degree of substitution of 0.7, compared to 40 % when the degree of substitution was 1.7 (Samios et al., 1997). Also, cellulose acetate with a degree of substitution of 2.2 lost ≈ 5 % of its weight after being submerged in seawater for one year (Yadav and Hakkarainen, 2022).

Poly(butylene succinate) presents a low degradation rate compared to other biopolymers, losing around 25 % and 2 % of its weight when it was exposed to industrial compost (58 ± 2 °C, 53.1 % relative humidity) and garden soil conditions (30 ± 2 °C, 55.6 % relative humidity) during six months, respectively (Puchalski et al., 2018). In addition, based on CO₂ measurements, a degradation rate of 20.3 % was reported when this material was exposed to the seawater-sediment interface for 6 months (Kim et al., 2024). In contrast, cellophane is fully recyclable in composting environments (Saha Dr et al., 2019), losing the 71 % of its mass after being buried for 5 months at 58 ± 2 °C and 55 % relative humidity (Erdal and Hakkarainen, 2022). Therefore, the low degradation rate of Material B compared to Material A under simulated sediment conditions can be associated with the presence of poly(butylene succinate).

3.1.2. FTIR

The spectrum of Material A underwent noticeable changes throughout the experiment, with the intensity of the different bands decreasing with time (Fig. S1; Table S5). I_{C=O} exhibited a significant decrease of 81 % (euphotic zone) and 77 % (aphotic zone), while I_{C-O} exhibited a significant decrease of 79 % (euphotic zone) and 72 % (aphotic zone), after 12 months (Fig. 2). Both indices also decreased under sediment conditions. However, since the plastics buried in sediment were almost completely degraded by month 6, FTIR analyses of these samples could not be performed between months 6 and 12 of the experiment. Under sediment conditions, both I_{C=O} and I_{C-O} exhibited a slight increase during months three and four but decreased again at month five. This behavior reflects the non-linear dynamics of polymer degradation due to environmental heterogeneity (i.e. variations in microbial diversity and abundance within sediment). Therefore, rather than focusing on short-term fluctuations, it is essential to consider the overall temporal trends of each index to better understand the underlying degradation mechanisms.

The loss of the C=O and C-O groups in cellulose acetate indicates deacetylation, which is produced by enzymes known as acylesterases (Erdal and Hakkarainen, 2022). Changes in the I_{O-H} were also observed

Fig. 1. Trends of weight loss (mean \pm SE, $n = 3$) undergone by: a) Material A; b) Material B. Aphotic and euphotic stand for the aphotic and euphotic zones of the water column, respectively. Weight loss at time 0 was 0 % for both materials, but it is not shown in the plots to facilitate data visualization. The weight loss of the materials for all conditions was measured simultaneously, but at each measuring time values of different conditions are slightly displaced to facilitate data visualization. The regression model was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) with $R^2 = 0.94$. Coefficients of the regression are shown in Table S6.

Fig. 2. FTIR indices of material A (mean \pm SE; $n = 3$) along time: a) $I_{C=O}$; b) I_{C-O} ; c) I_{O-H} . Aphotic and euphotic stand for the aphotic and euphotic zones of the water column, respectively. The FTIR analysis of the materials for all conditions was measured simultaneously, but at each measuring time values of different conditions are slightly displaced to facilitate data visualization. All regression models were statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). The R^2 of the regressions of $I_{C=O}$, I_{C-O} and I_{O-H} were 0.86, 0.86 and 0.63 respectively. Coefficients of the regressions are shown in Table S7.

across all treatments. Initially, I_{O-H} , along with $I_{C=O}$ and I_{C-O} , decreased significantly during the first month, decreasing 47 %, 37 % and 51 % under sediment, aphotic and euphotic zones, respectively. This decline may indicate the mineralization of low molecular weight fragments and exposed end groups of the material's surface (Phua et al., 2012). I_{O-H} increased consistently month by month from month one to month five in the sediment and aphotic zones, possibly due to the decrease in the degree of acetylation of the polymer (de Freitas et al., 2017), that leads to hydrogen bonding between the hydroxyl groups of cellulose molecules (Yadav and Hakkarainen, 2022); and due to the scission of the internal glycosidic bonds of the cellulose chain by endoglucanases (Polman et al., 2021). Although usually deacetylation is a slower rate determining step compared with the enzymatic degradation of the C-O-C ether linkages in the cellulose backbone, these processes can occur synergistically when cellulose acetate has a degree of substitution < 0.9 because the polymer is highly water-soluble (Puls et al., 2011). This pattern in I_{O-H} suggests that the degradation of cellulose acetate in the absence of light is mainly driven by enzymatic activity.

In contrast, I_{O-H} in the euphotic zone fluctuated irregularly during this same period, with alternating increases and decreases. These fluctuations may reflect the simultaneous action of multiple degradation mechanisms. On the one hand, the overall lower values of the three indices under euphotic conditions compared to aphotic conditions suggest that photo-oxidation caused by UV irradiance induced important changes in the chemical structure of polymer surface, accelerating surface mineralization by enhancing the activity of specific deacetylating enzymes, such as lipase, esterase, and cellulase (Erdal and Hakkarainen, 2022; Ishigaki et al., 2002). On the other hand, increases in I_{O-H} suggest partial deacetylation and enzymatic hydrolysis of the cellulose backbone. Together, these patterns indicate a complex degradation pathway under light exposure, driven by the interplay of abiotic and biotic processes. In addition, for the water column treatments, the I_{O-H} is notably reduced from month six to the end of the experiment, suggesting a partial mineralization of the polymer by microorganisms.

The bands of the chemical spectrum of the cellophane component of Material B underwent a similar decrease throughout the experiment (Fig. S2). The I_{C-O} exhibited a significant reduction of 71 %, 72 % and 72 % in sediment and aphotic and euphotic zones, respectively (Fig. 3; Table S5), without significant differences among the environmental compartments. The I_{O-H} also decreased significantly during the first half year of the experiment and increased between months 6 and 12. This increase was, albeit non-significant, more pronounced under sediment conditions, followed by the euphotic zone of the water column. As cellulose is a hydrophilic polymer, the degradation of this material may result from chemical and enzymatic hydrolysis, involving the random chain scission of the β -1,4-glycosidic bonds that link the glucose monomers of the cellulose backbone (Kim et al., 2006) and resulting in a reduction of C-O bonds and newly formed O-H bonds. In addition, UV radiation can promote the breaking of the polymer surface (Shashoua et al., 2024) and induce the formation of OH radicals, which can be incorporated into the cellophane structure, leading to the formation of O-H groups (Benyathiar et al., 2015). Also, as cellophane is a highly biodegradable polymer, the reduction of the indices may indicate a partial mineralization of some fractions of the polymer.

For poly(butylene succinate), all indices ($I_{C=O}$, I_{C-O-C} and I_{C-H}) were significantly reduced over time in all environmental compartments, with a notable decrease during the first month ($I_{C=O} > 39$ %; $I_{C-O-C} > 46$ %; $I_{C-H} > 60$ %), followed by small fluctuations until the end of the experiment (Fig. 4; Fig. S3; Table S5). The degradation of this biopolymer in the three environmental compartments can be attributed to abiotic hydrolysis reactions of ester bonds in the polymer backbone (Vieira et al., 2013), resulting in the reduction of $I_{C=O}$ and I_{C-O-C} (H. S. Kim et al., 2006). Additionally, enzymatic hydrolysis may occur at the polymer surface (Laycock et al., 2017), and the attached microorganisms can mineralize the polymer, further reducing $I_{C=O}$, I_{C-O-C} and I_{C-H} (Phua et al., 2012). The fluctuations (slight increases and decreases in

Fig. 3. FTIR indices of material B (cellophane) (mean \pm SE; $n = 3$) along time: a) $I_{C=O}$; b) I_{OH} . Aphotic and euphotic stand for the aphotic and euphotic zones of the water column, respectively. The FTIR analysis of the materials for all conditions was measured simultaneously, but at each measuring time values of different conditions are slightly displaced to facilitate data visualization. Both regression models were statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). The R^2 of the regressions of $I_{C=O}$ and I_{OH} were 0.83 and 0.66 respectively. Coefficients of the regressions are shown in Table S8.

the indices over time) from month one onward reflect the complexity of the biotic and abiotic processes and steps involved in the degradation of polymers under varying natural conditions. Furthermore, the minor differences observed in the trends of the indices across the three environmental compartments may be attributed to variability among certain replicates, which may be associated to the presence of microenvironments within microcosms, including slight variations in oxygen concentrations, temperature and microbial activity (Collins et al., 2025).

Our results suggest the usefulness of the proposed indices to study the degradation mechanisms of bio-based polymers and highlight the relevance of the chemical structure in the degradation rate of biodegradable/compostable materials. Functional groups like esters, ethers, and hydroxyls, present in polymers such as cellulose-based polymers (including cellulose acetate and cellophane), increase the hydrophilicity, facilitating abiotic and enzymatic hydrolysis of the polymer (Huang et al., 2022), which are important degradation mechanisms of biodegradable polymers. In contrast, the presence of C-H bonds in aliphatic polyesters, such as poly(butylene succinate), increases the hydrophobicity of the polymer, being more susceptible to other degradation mechanisms such as photodegradation (Min et al., 2020), which is quite limited in aquatic environments. Therefore, the degradation process will be accelerated if the polymer includes “weak links”, which increase its hydrophilicity. In addition, increased hydrophilicity enhances the adhesion of microorganisms to the surface of the polymer, accelerating the degradation rate (Arkatkar et al., 2009).

3.1.3. Thermal analysis

3.1.3.1. DSC. In the DSC thermogram of Material A and in the cellophane component of Material B, no clear melting and crystallization curves were observed. This is because cellulose-derived polymers present a lower crystallinity due to the introduction of substituents, presenting an amorphous structure (Dai et al., 2014). Therefore, results of this technique associated with these materials are not shown in this study.

The melting temperature (T_m) of poly(butylene succinate) exhibited small variations in all environmental compartments during the course of the experiment (112.5 ± 1 °C), suggesting that this parameter is not influenced by biotic and abiotic factors during the degradation process (Fig. 5; Table S6). Under sediment conditions, the ΔH_m of poly(butylene succinate) exhibited a significant increase of 43 ± 4.6 % after one year. Under conditions simulating the water column, a slight increase in ΔH_m was observed under the euphotic zone and the aphotic zone, compared to the non-degraded material (Fig. 5; Fig. S4; Table S6). This increase in the ΔH_m is associated to an increase in the crystallinity of the material (Lv et al., 2015). Poly(butylene succinate) is a semicrystalline material,

being its amorphous part the one that is degraded first (Kim et al., 2023). The amorphous regions of a polymer are more susceptible to degradation, as reacting species (e.g., solvents, enzymes, and oxygen) can penetrate through the disordered regions more easily (Pischedda et al., 2019). As a result, the degradation of these regions is enhanced by microbial activity, among other factors, which explains the greater increase in AHm in the polymer exposed to sediment compared to the water column. As the amorphous region degrades, the crystallinity of the material increases, which in turn leads to a reduction of its degradation rate as these crystalline regions are less susceptible to biological activity (Tokiwa and Calabia, 2006). This explains why the increase in AHm slows down during the final months of the experiment.

The present results show that cellulose-derived polymers with an amorphous structure present a higher degree of degradation than semicrystalline polymers. However, as observed for poly(butylene succinate), biotic and abiotic processes still occur for semicrystalline polymers, (mainly in environments with high microbial activity as marine sediments), but the higher the crystallinity, the slower the processes will be (Kim et al., 2023). This highlights the importance of crystallinity in the degradation rate of biodegradable/compostable materials, being an essential feature that needs to be considered to develop fast-degradable materials in the environment.

3.1.3.2. TGA. T_{peak} of Material A exposed to water column conditions was substantially reduced, decreasing from 338 ± 0 °C to 296 ± 12 °C (12.3 ± 3.6 %) and to 259 ± 3 °C (23.3 ± 1.0 %) in the aphotic and euphotic zones, respectively, after one year (Fig. 6, Fig. S5, Table S7). These results highlight a partial loss of the material’s thermal stability and further suggest that light accelerates the overall degradation of cellulose acetate. Under sediment conditions T_{peak} followed a similar trend than under the two water column compartments during the first 6 months of the experiment (Fig. 6b, Fig. S5, Table S7). Although there are no TGA results for plastics buried in sediment after the sixth month due to the almost complete degradation of the samples, T_{peak} of buried samples would be expected to follow a similar trend to that of the samples exposed to the water column, decreasing markedly after one year.

Regarding material B, T_{peak} of cellophane exhibited a noticeable, albeit non-significant, decrease, reducing from 307 ± 0 °C to 234 ± 5 °C (23.7 ± 1.6 %), 244 ± 3 °C (20.5 ± 2.2 %) and 241 ± 7 °C (21.6 ± 0.1 %) when the material was exposed to sediment, aphotic and euphotic conditions for one year, respectively (Fig. 6d, Fig. S6, Table S7). These results confirm that the thermal properties of cellophane are modified through a reduction of its thermal stability disregarding the environmental conditions. In contrast, T_{peak} of poly(butylene succinate) was almost unaffected by the environmental compartment, decreasing from

Fig. 4. FTIR indices of material B (poly(butylene succinate)) (mean \pm SE; $n = 3$) along time: a) $I_{C=O}$; b) I_{C-O-C} ; c) I_{C-H} . Aphotic and euphotic stand for the aphotic and euphotic zones of the water column, respectively. The FTIR analysis of the materials for all conditions was measured simultaneously, but at each measuring time values of different conditions are slightly displaced to facilitate data visualization. All regression models were statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). The R^2 values for the regressions of $I_{C=O}$, I_{C-O-C} and I_{C-H} were 0.65, 0.72 and 0.56 respectively. Coefficients of the regressions are shown in Table S8.

391 ± 0 °C to 383 ± 3 °C (1.9 ± 0.7 %) after its exposure to sediment, and to 388 ± 0 °C (0.1 ± 0.2 %) and 390 ± 1 °C (0.8 ± 0.1 %) after its exposure to aphotic and euphotic conditions for one year, respectively (Fig. 6f, Fig. S6, Table S7). These findings suggest one more time that poly(butylene succinate) is less biodegradable than the other bio-based polymers under the tested conditions.

A notable loss of thermal stability has been observed in other biopolymers, such as poly(lactic acid), poly(ϵ -caprolactone), poly(butylene succinate adipate) and poly(3-hydroxybutyrate) under sand conditions after 267 days (De Falco et al., 2021). The exposure to environmental conditions led to polymer degradation including the cleavage of polymer chains and the subsequent formation of low molecular weight compounds (Chen et al., 2024). These compounds present a lower thermal stability being more easily degraded, thus lowering the T_{peak} values (Moraczewski et al., 2019). However, in accordance with the T_{peak} of poly(butylene succinate), the T_{peak} of polybutylene adipate terephthalate underwent a slight decrease when buried in compost conditions for 45 days (Ruggero et al., 2020), indicating the usefulness of this parameter to understand and monitor the loss of thermal stability of biodegradable plastics after being exposed to different environmental conditions.

The activation energy exhibited a notable decrease throughout the experiment. For Material A, the E_a decreased from 211.3 ± 0 kJ/mol (E_a at time 0) to 181.2 ± 21.8 kJ/mol (14.2 ± 10.3 %) and 153.2 ± 6.0 kJ/mol (27.5 ± 2.8 %) after 12 months in the aphotic and euphotic zones of the water column, respectively (Fig. 6; Table S7). As for T_{peak} , E_a of buried samples could only be calculated for the first 6 months of the experiment because samples were almost complete degraded. During these months, E_a of buried samples exhibited a noticeable decrease compared to the two compartments of the water column. In this sense, a more marked reduction in E_a under sediment conditions compared to water column conditions is expected after one year of experiment.

The E_a value of cellophane underwent a noticeable, albeit non-significant, decreasing from 202.6 ± 0 kJ/mol (E_a at time 0) to 115.2 ± 13.5 kJ/mol (43.1 ± 6.6 %), 152.2 ± 10.7 kJ/mol (24.9 ± 5.3 %) and 161.1 ± 7.4 kJ/mol (20.5 ± 3.6 %), under aphotic, euphotic and sediment conditions, respectively, after 12 months. These results are consistent with weight loss trends, the higher reduction of E_a under aphotic conditions suggesting a more effective biotic degradation of this polymer in the absence of light. In addition, photodegradation is usually limited to superficial structural changes (Xu et al., 2024), whereas microbial degradation can proceed into deeper layers via bulk erosion mechanisms.

In the case of poly(butylene succinate), the reduction in E_a throughout the experiment was significantly high in the sediment (from 228.8 ± 0 to 200.4 ± 10.9 kJ/mol; 12.4 ± 4.8 %) and in the euphotic zone (from 228.8 ± 0 to 207.1 ± 3.0 kJ/mol; 9.5 ± 1.4 %) compared to the aphotic zone (from 228.8 ± 0 to 219.8 ± 3.0 kJ/mol; 3.9 ± 1.3 %) (Fig. 6; Table S7), buried samples exhibiting the highest decrease in the thermal stability. Other biodegradable materials, such as Mater-Bi, composed of polybutylene adipate terephthalate and starch, also suffered a decrease in E_a when exposed to compost conditions for 45 days (Ruggero et al., 2020), being lower in polybutylene adipate terephthalate (20 %) than in starch (57 %). This decrease in E_a suggest that all the studied polymers exhibited, to varying degrees, a decrease in molecular weight and a simplification of the polymer structure, associated to a degradation process.

3.2. Complementarity of the analytical methods

The studied parameters derived from the three analytical techniques, including the FTIR derived indices ($I_{C=O}$, I_{C-O} , I_{C-H} and I_{OH}), T_{peak} , E_a and ΔH_m , enabled the detection of specific mechanisms responsible for alterations in the chemical structure and the thermal stability of the polymers, and highlighting the relationship between chemical structure, crystallinity, and hydrophilicity. In this sense, our results indicate that

Fig. 5. a) Melting temperature (T_m); b) melting enthalpy (ΔH_m) (mean \pm SE; $n = 3$) obtained from the DSC thermogram of poly(butylene succinate) along time. Aphotic and euphotic stand for the aphotic and euphotic zones of the water column, respectively. The DSC analysis of the materials for all conditions was measured simultaneously, but at each measuring time values of different conditions are slightly displaced to facilitate data visualization. Both regression models were statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). The R^2 of the regressions of T_m and ΔH_m were 0.58 and 0.78, respectively. The coefficients of the regression are shown in [Table S9](#).

Fig. 6. Activation energy (E_a) and T_{peak} (mean \pm SE; $n = 3$) obtained from the TGA/DTG curves along time: a) and b) Material A; c) and d) Material B (cellophane); e) and f) Material B (poly(butylene succinate)). Aphotic and euphotic stand for the aphotic and euphotic zones of the water column, respectively. The TGA analysis of the materials for all conditions was measured simultaneously, but at each measuring time values of different conditions are slightly displaced to facilitate data visualization. All regression models were statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). The R^2 values for the regressions of E_a and T_{peak} were 0.34, 0.30, 0.41 and 0.68, 0.79 and 0.56, respectively, for Material A, Material B (cellophane) and Material B (poly(butylene succinate)). Coefficients of the regression are shown in [Table S10](#).

the degradation process of a biodegradable polymer in marine conditions will be slowed when it presents a high degree of crystallinity and a hydrophobic chemical structure, as it will initially undergo surface degradation in the amorphous regions. On the other hand, the

degradation rate will be accelerated if the polymer presents a hydrophilic and disordered structure, as it will degrade by bulk erosion since their rate of diffusion of water exceeds the rate of the hydrolysis reaction.

Our results show that degradation depends not only on the intrinsic characteristics of each material, but also on the environmental conditions to which they are exposed. For example, although light did not play an important role in the weight loss of the tested materials, it did produce significant structural and thermal changes in Material A. This material showed a greater, albeit non-significant, reduction of $I_{C=O}$, I_{C-O-C} and I_{OH} indices decreasing by 4 %, 7 % and 17 % respectively, and T_{peak} and E_a decreasing by 11 % and 13 %, respectively in the euphotic zone compared to the aphotic zone of the water column after one year. Additionally, in Material B, the cellophane layer underwent structural changes, with an increase in I_{OH} groups in sediment (12 %, suggesting enzymatic and chemical hydrolysis) and the euphotic zone (23 %, suggesting photochemical degradation) compared to the aphotic zone at the end of the experiment. However, cellophane showed a higher reduction in activation energy under aphotic conditions. The layer of poly (butylene succinate) also underwent chemical structural changes, with all FTIR indices decreasing by over 50 % across all compartments by the end of the experiment. However, a greater reduction in E_a was observed under sediment (8 %) and euphotic zone (6 %) compared to the aphotic zone after one year. Also, ΔH_m revealed a significant reduction of the amorphous regions of poly(butylene succinate) when buried in sediment, while no changes were observed in the water column.

These results demonstrate that the combined use of FTIR, DSC and TGA derived metrics, along with weight loss, offer complementary insights into the specific degradation mechanisms of each polymer across different environmental compartments.

4. Conclusions

The degradation of the studied bio-based materials was strongly influenced by the environmental compartment, with degradation occurring approximately five times faster in sediment compared to the water column. This highlights the key role of microbial activity in the degradation process of biodegradable polymers. In addition, although light did not play a key role in the weight loss of the materials submerged in the water column, it promoted chemical and thermal changes, with effects varying depending on the specific material.

The combined use of FTIR, DSC and TGA provided a holistic assessment of the distinct degradation mechanisms of each material and highlighted the influence of environmental factors such as light exposure and microbial activity. Specifically, FTIR-derived indices were useful to understand the abiotic and biotic pathways of degradation of the studied materials, which were highly dependent on their hydrophilicity and crystallinity. TGA-derived parameters (T_{peak} and E_a) enabled to detect the loss of thermal stability and the simplification of the chemical structure, especially pronounced in cellulose-derived polymers. In the case of DSC, ΔH_m was useful to understand variations on the amorphous/crystalline regions.

Overall, these findings demonstrate that parameters such as weight loss, FTIR indices, T_{peak} , E_a and ΔH_m provide complementary insights and should be analyzed together to comprehensively understand the degradation process of biodegradable and compostable materials. Employing this integrated approach can significantly support the design and development of more sustainable and environmentally friendly materials. Furthermore, the presented findings underscore the importance of developing technical standards that certify material degradability across ecosystems integrating environmental compartments with contrasting conditions.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alba Benito-Kaesbach: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Ana Beltrán-Sanahuja:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Robert T. Mathers:** Writing – review & editing. **Carlos Sanz-Lázaro:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Funding

This work was supported by the University of Alicante (PC20-04B; and UAU2123-19). This study forms part of the ThinkInAzul programme and was supported by MICIU with funding from European Union NextGenerationEU (PRTR-C17.I1) and by Generalitat Valenciana (GVA-THINKINAZUL/2021/041; principal investigators: C. Sanz-Lázaro, A. Beltrán-Sanahuja, University of Alicante). This manuscript is published as part of the project “Viable, safe and sustainable PHBV value chain for food packaging applications (ViSS)” under a CreativeCommon Public Domain Dedication. ViSS was Co – Funded by the European Union, grant number 101081931. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, REA or UKRI. Neither the European Union nor the granting authorities can be held responsible for them.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

We thank Nuria Casado Coy and Francisco Asensio Montesinos for their help in the running of the experiments. Alba Benito Kaesbach was supported by the pre-doctoral contract (Ref: CIACIF/2021/328) funded by Generalitat Valenciana (Conselleria de Educación, Cultura, Universidades y Empleo) and Fondo Social Europeo Plus.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2025.146435>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Aqil, M., Abderrahim, B., Abderrahman, E., Mohamed, A., Fatima, T., Abdesselam, T., Krim, O., 2015. Kinetic thermal degradation of cellulose, polybutylene succinate and a green composite: comparative Study. *World Journal of Environmental Engineering* 3 (4), 95–110. <https://doi.org/10.12691/wjee-3-4-1>.
- Arkatkar, A., Arutchelvi, J., Sudhakar, M., Bhaduri, S., Uppara, P.V., Doble, M., 2009. Approaches to enhance the biodegradation of polyolefins. In: *The Open Environmental Engineering Journal*, vol. 2.
- Barragán, D.H., Pelacho, A.M., Martín-Closas, L., 2016. Degradation of agricultural biodegradable plastics in the soil under laboratory conditions. *Soil Res.* 54 (2), 216–224. <https://doi.org/10.1071/SR15034>.
- Beltrán-Sanahuja, A., Casado-Coy, N., Simó-Cabrera, L., Sanz-Lázaro, C., 2020. Monitoring polymer degradation under different conditions in the marine environment. *Environ. Pollut.* 259. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2019.113836>.
- Benyathir, P., Selke, S., Auras, R., 2015. Effect of irradiation on the biodegradation of cellophane films. *J. Polym. Environ.* 23, 449–458.
- Blott, S.J., Pye, K., 2012. Particle size scales and classification of sediment types based on particle size distributions: review and recommended procedures. *Sedimentology* 59 (7), 2071–2096. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3091.2012.01335.x>.
- Briassoulis, D., Dejean, C., Picuno, P., 2010. Critical review of norms and standards for biodegradable agricultural plastics Part II: composting. In: *Journal of Polymers and the Environment*, vol. 18, pp. 364–383. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10924-010-0222-z>.
- Briassoulis, D., Pikasi, A., Briassoulis, C., Mistriotis, A., 2019. Disintegration behaviour of bio-based plastics in coastal zone marine environments: a field experiment under natural conditions. *Sci. Total Environ.* 688, 208–223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.06.129>.
- Chen, Z., Zhang, X., Fu, Y., Jin, Y., Weng, Y., Bian, X., Chen, X., 2024. Degradation behaviors of polylactic acid, polyglycolic acid, and their copolymer films in simulated marine environments. *Polymers* 16 (13), 1765.
- Collins, H.I., Tabb, L., Holohan, B.A., Ward, J.E., 2025. Disintegration of biodegradable plastic bags in Marine Mesocosm conditions: the effects of time and temperature. *J. Polym. Environ.* 33 (2), 1035–1046.

- Dai, L., Wang, L.Y., Yuan, T.Q., He, J., 2014. Study on thermal degradation kinetics of cellulose-graft-poly(L-lactic acid) by thermogravimetric analysis. *Polym. Degrad. Stabil.* 99 (1), 233–239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2013.10.024>.
- De Falco, F., Avolio, R., Errico, M.E., Di Pace, E., Avella, M., Cocca, M., Gentile, G., 2021. Comparison of biodegradable polyesters degradation behavior in sand. *J. Hazard Mater.* 416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.126231>.
- de Freitas, R.R.M., Senna, A.M., Botaro, V.R., 2017. Influence of degree of substitution on thermal dynamic mechanical and physicochemical properties of cellulose acetate. *Ind. Crop. Prod.* 109, 452–458. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2017.08.062>.
- de Vogel, F.A., Goudriaan, M., Zettler, E.R., Niemann, H., Eich, A., Weber, M., et al., 2024. Biodegradable plastics in Mediterranean coastal environments feature contrasting microbial succession. *Sci. Total Environ.* 928, 172288.
- Delacuvellerie, A., Benali, S., Cyriaque, V., Moins, S., Raquez, J.M., Gobert, S., Wattiez, R., 2021. Microbial biofilm composition and polymer degradation of compostable and non-compostable plastics immersed in the marine environment. *J. Hazard Mater.* 419. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.126526>.
- Erdal, N.B., Hakkarainen, M., 2022. Degradation of cellulose derivatives in laboratory, Man-Made, and natural environments. In: *Biomacromolecules*, vol. 23. American Chemical Society, pp. 2713–2729. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.biomac.2c00336>, 7.
- European Bioplastics, 2023. <https://www.european-bioplastics.org/bioplastics-market-development-update-2023-2/>.
- European Commission, 2022. EU. Policy Framework on Biobased, Biodegradable and Compostable Plastics.
- Fei, P., Liao, L., Cheng, B., Song, J., 2017. Quantitative analysis of cellulose acetate with a high degree of substitution by FTIR and its application. *Anal. Methods* 9 (43), 6194–6201. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c7ay02165h>.
- Georgousopoulou, I.N., Vouyiouka, S., Dole, P., Papispyrides, C.D., 2016. Thermo-mechanical degradation and stabilization of poly(butylene succinate). *Polym. Degrad. Stabil.* 128, 182–192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2016.03.012>.
- Geyer, R., Jambeck, J.R., Law, K.L., 2017. Production, use, and fate of all plastics ever made. *Sci. Adv.* <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1700782>.
- Haider, T.P., Völker, C., Kramm, J., Landfester, K., Wurm, F.R., 2019. Kunststoffe der Zukunft? Der Einfluss von bioabbaubaren Polymeren auf Umwelt und Gesellschaft. *Angew. Chem.* 131 (1), 50–63. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ange.201805766>.
- He, Y., Li, H., Xiao, X., Zhao, X., 2021. Polymer degradation: category, mechanism and development prospect. *E3S Web of Conferences* 290. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202129001012>.
- Huang, C., Liao, Y., Zou, Z., Chen, Y., Jin, M., Zhu, J., Hussain Abdalkarim, S.Y., Zhou, Y., Yu, H.Y., 2022. Novel strategy to interpret the degradation behaviors and mechanisms of bio- and non-degradable plastics. *J. Clean. Prod.* 355. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.131757>.
- Ishigaki, T., Sugano, W., Ike, M., Taniguchi, H., Goto, T., Fujita, M., 2002. Effect of UV irradiation on enzymatic degradation of cellulose acetate. *Polym. Degrad. Stabil.* 78 (3), 505–510.
- Jambeck, Jenna R., Geyer, Roland, Wilcox, Chris, Siegler, Theodore R., Perryman, Miriam, Andrady, Anthony, Narayan, Ramani, Law, Kara Lavender, 2015. Plastic waste inputs from land into the ocean. *Science* 347 (6223), 764–768. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1260879>.
- Kim, H.S., Kim, H.J., Lee, J.W., Choi, I.G., 2006. Biodegradability of bio-flour filled biodegradable poly(butylene succinate) bio-composites in natural and compost soil. *Polym. Degrad. Stabil.* 91 (5), 1117–1127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2005.07.002>.
- Kim, M.S., Chang, H., Zheng, L., Yan, Q., Pflieger, B.F., Klier, J., Nelson, K., Majumder, E. L.W., Huber, G.W., 2023. A review of biodegradable plastics: chemistry, applications, properties, and future research needs. In: *Chemical Reviews*, vol. 123. American Chemical Society, pp. 9915–9939. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.2c00876>, 16.
- Kumar Sen, S., Raut, S., 2015. Microbial degradation of low density polyethylene (LDPE): a review. In: *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*, vol. 3. Elsevier Ltd, pp. 462–473. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2015.01.003>, 1.
- Lambert, S., Wagner, M., 2017. Environmental performance of bio-based and biodegradable plastics: the road ahead. In: *Chemical Society Reviews*, vol. 46. Royal Society of Chemistry, pp. 6855–6871. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c7cs00149e>, 22.
- Laycock, B., Nikolić, M., Colwell, J.M., Gauthier, E., Halley, P., Bottle, S., George, G., 2017. Lifetime prediction of biodegradable polymers. In: *Progress in Polymer Science*, vol. 71. Elsevier Ltd, pp. 144–189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2017.02.004>.
- Leppänen, I., Vikman, M., Harlin, A., Orelma, H., 2020. Enzymatic degradation and pilot-scale composting of cellulose-based films with different chemical structures. *J. Polym. Environ.* 28 (2), 458–470. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10924-019-01621-w>.
- Lv, Y., Huang, Y., Yang, J., Kong, M., Yang, H., Zhao, J., Li, G., 2015. Outdoor and accelerated laboratory weathering of polypropylene: a comparison and correlation study. *Polym. Degrad. Stabil.* 112, 145–159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2014.12.023>.
- Mano, J. F., Koniárova, D., & Reis, R. L. Thermal Properties of Thermoplastic starch/Synthetic Polymer Blends with Potential Biomedical Applicability.
- Marín, A., Feijóo, P., Carbonetto, B., González-Torres, P., Tena-Medialdea, J., García-March, J.R., et al., 2025. Long-term monitoring of biofilm succession unveils differences between biodegradable and conventional plastic materials. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 214, 117820.
- Middelburg, J.J., Vluc, T., Jaco, F., Van Der Nat, W.A., 1993. Organic matter mineralization in marine systems. In: *Global and Planetary Change*, vol. 8.
- Min, K., Cuffi, J.D., Mathers, R.T., 2020. Ranking environmental degradation trends of plastic marine debris based on physical properties and molecular structure. *Nat. Commun.* 11 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-14538-z>.
- Moraczewski, K., Stepczyńska, M., Malinowski, R., Karasiewicz, T., Jagodziński, B., Rytlewski, P., 2019. The effect of accelerated aging on polylactide containing plant extracts. *Polymers* 11 (4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym11040575>.
- Napper, I.E., Thompson, R.C., 2019. Environmental deterioration of biodegradable, Oxo-biodegradable, compostable, and conventional plastic carrier bags in the Sea, soil, and open-air over a 3-Year period. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 53 (9), 4775–4783. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.8b06984>.
- Nazareth, M., Marques, M.R.C., Leite, M.C.A., Castro, Í.B., 2019. Commercial plastics claiming biodegradable status: is this also accurate for marine environments? *J. Hazard Mater.* 366, 714–722. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2018.12.052>.
- Nazareth, M.C., Marques, M.R.C., Pinheiro, L.M., Castro, Í.B., 2022. Key issues for bio-based, biodegradable and compostable plastics governance. In: *Journal of Environmental Management*, vol. 322. Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.116074>.
- Odobel, C., Dussud, C., Philip, L., Derippe, G., Lauters, M., Eyheraguibel, B., et al., 2021. Bacterial abundance, diversity and activity during long-term colonization of non-biodegradable and biodegradable plastics in seawater. *Front. Microbiol.* 12, 734782.
- Phua, Y.J., Lau, N.S., Sudesh, K., Chow, W.S., Mohd Ishak, Z.A., 2012. Biodegradability studies of poly(butylene succinate)/organo-montmorillonite nanocomposites under controlled compost soil conditions: effects of clay loading and compatibiliser. *Polym. Degrad. Stabil.* 97 (8), 1345–1354. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2012.05.024>.
- Phua, Y.J., Chow, W.S., Mohd Ishak, Z.A., 2013. Reactive processing of maleic anhydride-grafted poly(butylene succinate) and the compatibilizing effect on poly(butylene succinate) nanocomposites. *Express Polym. Lett.* 7 (4), 340–354. <https://doi.org/10.3144/expresspolymlett.2013.31>.
- Pischedda, A., Tosin, M., Degli-Innocenti, F., 2019. Biodegradation of plastics in soil: the effect of temperature. *Polym. Degrad. Stabil.* 170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2019.109017>.
- Polman, E.M.N., Gruter, G.J.M., Parsons, J.R., Tietema, A., 2021. Comparison of the aerobic biodegradation of biopolymers and the corresponding bioplastics: a review. In: *Science of the Total Environment*, vol. 753. Elsevier B.V. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.141953>.
- Puchalski, M., Szparaga, G., Biela, T., Gutowska, A., Sztajnowski, S., Krucińska, I., 2018. Molecular and supramolecular changes in polybutylene succinate (PBS) and polybutylene succinate adipate (PBSA) copolymer during degradation in various environmental conditions. *Polymers* 10 (3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym10030251>.
- Puls, J., Wilson, S.A., Hölter, D., 2011. Degradation of cellulose acetate-based materials: a review. In: *Journal of Polymers and the Environment*, vol. 19, pp. 152–165. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10924-010-0258-0>, 1.
- Ribeiro, S.D., Meneguim, A.B., Barud, H. da S., Silva, J.M., Oliveira, R.L., Asunção, R. M. N. de, Torrin, T.F., Muñoz, R.A.A., Filho, G.R., Ribeiro, C.A., 2022. Synthesis and characterization of cellulose acetate from cellophane industry residues. Application as acetaminophen controlled-release membranes. *J. Therm. Anal. Calorimetry* 147 (13), 7265–7275. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-021-11022-8>.
- Ruggero, F., Carretti, E., Gori, R., Lotti, T., Lubello, C., 2020. Monitoring of degradation of starch-based biopolymer film under different composting conditions, using TGA, FTIR and SEM analysis. *Chemosphere* 246. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2019.125770>.
- Saha Dr, N.C., Madhu Dr, G., Kadu Ms, D.B., 2019. Evaluation of biodegradability characteristics of cellulose-based film as per IS/ISO 14855-1. *Journal of Applied Packaging Research* 11 (3), 2.
- Samos, E., Dart, R.K., Dawkins, J.V., 1997. Preparation, characterization and biodegradation studies on cellulose acetates with varying degrees of substitution, 38 (Issue 12).
- Sander, B. C., & Kalf, J. Factors controlling bacterial production in marine and freshwater sediments. In *Source: Microbial Ecology* (Vol. vol. 26, Issue 2).
- Shashoua, Y., Peydaei, A., Mortensen, M.N., Kanstrup, A.B., Gregory, D.J., 2024. Physico-chemical degradation of single-use plastics in natural weather and marine environments. *Environ. Pollut.* 357, 124414.
- Skvorčinskienė, R., Kiminaitė, I., Vorotinskienė, L., Jančiauskas, A., Paulauskas, R., 2023. Complex study of bioplastics: degradation in soil and characterization by FTIR-ATR and FTIR-TGA methods. *Energy* 274. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2023.127320>.
- Smith, I.L., Stanton, T., Law, A., 2021. Plastic habitats: algal biofilms on photic and aphotic plastics. *J. Hazard. Mater. Lett.* 2, 100038. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/282732/global-production-of-plastics-since-1950/> (2024).
- Sudhakar, M., Doble, M., Murthy, P.S., Venkatesan, R., 2008. Marine microbe-mediated biodegradation of low- and high-density polyethylenes. *Int. Biodeterior. Biodegrad.* 61 (3), 203–213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibiod.2007.07.011>.
- Thellen, C., Coyne, M., Froio, D., Auerbach, M., Wirsén, C., Ratto, J.A., 2008. A processing, characterization and marine biodegradation study of melt-extruded polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA) films. *J. Polym. Environ.* 16 (1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10924-008-0079-6>.

- Tokiwa, Y., Calabia, B.P., 2006. Biodegradability and biodegradation of poly(lactide). In: *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology*, vol. 72, pp. 244–251. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-006-0488-1>, 2.
- United Nations Environment Programme, 2021. From Pollution to solution: a global assessment of marine litter and plastic pollution. <https://www.unep.org/>.
- Vieira, A.C., Guedes, R.M., Tita, V., 2013. Considerations for the design of polymeric biodegradable products. In: *Journal of Polymer Engineering*, vol. 33, pp. 293–302. <https://doi.org/10.1515/polyeng-2012-0150>, 4.
- Viera, J.S.C., Marques, M.R.C., Nazareth, M.C., Jimenez, P.C., Sanz-Lázaro, C., Castro, Í. B., 2021. Are biodegradable plastics an environmental rip off? *J. Hazard Mater.* 416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.125957>.
- Xu, Y., Ou, Q., van der Hoek, J.P., Liu, G., Lompe, K.M., 2024. Photo-oxidation of micro- and nanoplastics: physical, chemical, and biological effects in environments. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 58 (2), 991–1009.
- Yadav, N., Hakkarainen, M., 2022. Degradation of cellulose acetate in simulated aqueous environments: One-Year Study. *Macromol. Mater. Eng.* 307 (6). <https://doi.org/10.1002/mame.202100951>.